

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE FIBRE BRIDGING FRACTURE TOUGHENING MECHANISM OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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INTRODUCTION

- The study investigated **large scale fibre bridging (LSFB)** in unidirectional CFRP specimens.
- **Double cantilever beam** tests were conducted to measure the interlaminar fracture toughness under Mode I loading.
- The research examined the contribution of **fibre bridging to fracture toughness** using R-curves.
- The results showed that all specimens exhibited **rising R-curves**, indicating **significant fibre bridging effects**.
- **Fibre cutting** was performed to gain insights into the contribution of fibre bridging in a double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen.

TEST METHOD

Schematic showing how a defect in the processing zone ahead the crack tip can grow into the primary crack and cause fibres to bridge the crack.

Photograph taken of a DCB specimen during testing, in which this phenomena is shown.

Typical R-curve plot ($G_{IC} - a$) of a DCB experiencing Large Scale Fibre Bridging (LSFB) with key values identified.

$G_{I,init}$ (J/m^2)	$G_{I,prop}$ (J/m^2)	$G_{I,prop-init}$ (J/m^2)	R-curve length (mm)
337.39 ± 53.57	1315.50 ± 93.90	978.11 ± 108.10	30.50 ± 0.55

Averaged results of all DCB specimens tested.

FIBRE BRIDGING EXPERIMENT

Illustration defining the fibre cut length, c , the crack growth length, Δa , and the length of fibre bridging zone still intact, $\Delta a - c$.

Plot of the recovered fractured energy ΔG_{IC} as the fibre bridging zone is cut.

Derivative of the fitted logistic function above.

The resistance distribution of the fibres bridging.

Visual demonstration of the measured R-curve length and the onset of the bridging zone, $(\Delta a - c)_{onset}$, overlaid on a DCB specimen.

CONCLUSIONS

- The 'effective' bridging zone length obtained via the fibre cutting experiment showed good correlation to the R-curve length.
- The fibre cutting experiment quantitatively evaluated fibre contribution to fracture energy based on distance from the crack.
- The resistance distribution of the fibre bridging shows good correlation to typically assumed bridging laws.